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AI AND ROBOTICS IN CONSTRUCTION

@ ERF 2023

EUROPEAN
ROBOTICS FORUM

eu ROBOTICS at the heart

AI

ORGANISERS

Antonio Alonso CEPEDA
ACCIONA

Dimitrios GIAKOURIS
CERTH-ITI

Jason RAMBACH
DFKI

Christian SCHLETTE
SDU

www.beeyonders.eu

www.humantech-horizon.eu

www.robetarme-project.eu

AGENDA

15 March 2023 11:05-12:25

Odense, Denmark

PART 01

11:05 - 12:00

WORKSHOP INTRODUCTION AND OVERVIEW

INSIGHTS ON THE EC AIMS IN THE SCOPE OF AI AND ROBOTICS IN CONSTRUCTION

Dr. Dimitrios Biliouris
Project Adviser - European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)

AI AND ROBOTICS IN SHOTCRETING ACTIVITIES - THE ROBOTARME PROJECT CASE

Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis
RobotArme project Coordinator

HUMANTECH PROJECT OVERVIEW

Dr. Jason Rambach
HumanTech project Coordinator

BEEYONDERS PROJECT OVERVIEW

Mr. Antonio Alonso Cepeda
Beeyonders project Coordinator

OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR AI AND ROBOTICS IN CONSTRUCTION FROM THE END USER'S POINT OF VIEW

Jonas Bentzen
Christiansen & Essenbæk A/S, Project Manager

Fernando Sigchos Jiménez
European Builders Confederation, Secretary General

Patrick Roth
Implenia, New Business and Innovation Manager

12:05 - 12:25

PART 02

ROUND TABLE

Mads Essenbaek
Christiansen & Essenbæk A/S, Project Leader

Dr. Bharath Sankaran
Naska.AI

Dr. Gabor Sziebig
SINTEF

Mr. José Carlos Jiménez Fernández
Tecnalia

Dr. Antidio Viguria Jiménez
FADA CATEC

FEEDBACK ROUND WITH ATTENDEES

ORGANISERS

Mr. Antonio Alonso CEPEDA

Beeyonders project Coordinator

JOB TITLE

Innovation manager

AFFILIATION

ACCIONA Construction

BIO

MSc Industrial Engineer in Energetic Technologies and PMP. His technical background is based on two fields of knowledge:

1. Computer fluid mechanics and thermal analysis, developing algorithms to optimize engineering systems behavior applied to Energy Efficiency in Buildings, and
2. Robotics, working in the development of different prototypes for construction, and giving support to the company in Digital Transformation for Construction. His managing background has been focused on the ICT and Automation area into the technological Innovation Direction in Madrid (ACCIONA), giving advice to strategic decisions, new research lines, and managing groups of researchers. During these years, he has worked in several European projects related to Energy Efficiency and Robotics. Currently, he is the Project Manager of BEEYONDERS, which involves 21 partners with a budget of 8 M€ and 3.5 years.

Dr. Dimitrios GIAKOURIS

RobetArme project Coordinator

JOB TITLE

Researcher (Grade C)

AFFILIATION

Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH)

BIO

Dr. Dimitrios Giakouris is a Senior Researcher (Grade C) at the Information Technologies Institute of the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH). His main research interests include human-robot interaction, robot vision, service robot perception and cognition, affective computing, human motion, activity and behaviour analysis and modelling, safe and social-aware robot navigation, biosignals processing and sensor management, multimodal interfaces, machine learning and pattern recognition.

He has been working as a Researcher with ITI since February 2007 and he has been involved in more than 15 research projects, funded by the EC and the Greek Secretariat of Research and Technology. These include the Horizon 2020 RAMCIP, BADGER, HR-Recycler, Ageing@work and BACCHUS projects, where he also contributed to the Technical Coordination and Quality Management of the project consortium.

Dr. Jason RAMBACH

HumanTech project Coordinator

JOB TITLE

Senior Researcher, Team Leader Spatial Sensing and Machine Perception

AFFILIATION

German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence, DFKI

BIO

Jason Rambach received his PhD in Computer Science in 2020 from the University of Kaiserslautern for his dissertation entitled "Learning Priors for Augmented Reality Tracking and Scene Understanding". He has been at DFKI Augmented Vision in Kaiserslautern since 2015. Currently, he is a Senior Researcher leading the team "Spatial Sensing and Machine Perception" of approx. 10 researchers working on depth sensing and Geometric/Semantic scene understanding using Machine Learning.

His research interests include SLAM and Semantic Scene Understanding, Object Pose Estimation and Tracking, Anomaly Detection, Hybrid AI, Robotic Vision and Augmented Reality. He has over 40 publications in leading Computer Vision and Augmented Reality conferences, a best paper award from the IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR) 2017 and two awards at the BOP Object Pose Estimation challenge 2022 at ECCV. He is a reviewer for several scientific journals and conferences (CVPR, ECCV, ICRA, WACV, BMVC). Since 2022 he is coordinator of the EU Horizon Project HumanTech, applying AI in the construction industry for Scan2BIM, Wearables and Assistance Robots.

Christian SHLETTE

Head of SDU Center for Large Structure Production (LSP)

JOB TITLE

Professor

AFFILIATION

Center for Large Structure Production (LSP)

BIO

Christian Schlette is a Professor at the Mærsk Mc-Kinney Møller Institute (MMMI) at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU). He is heading SDU's Center for Large Structure Production (LSP), dedicated to strengthen the twin transition (green & digital) of the sectors energy, construction and maritime with novel robotization and digitalization solutions.

In his research, Christian is interested on synergies across the fields of automation, robotics, simulation and control in application areas such as factory automation and large structure production. He is working on workflows, methods and tools for model-, simulation, and data-based engineering of robot technologies (systems and services) by means of Digital Twins, multi-agent systems, sampling-based problem solving, database technologies and VR/AR interfaces. He is responsible for the design and implementation of robotic technologies (systems and services) in various national and international research projects with partners from academia and industry.

Christian received his Dipl.-Ing. in Electrical Engineering from the University of Dortmund, Germany in 2002 and joined the Robotics Research Institute (IRF) in Dortmund as research associate to develop control approaches for industrial multi-robot systems. In 2005/2006, he worked for EFR-Systems GmbH, Dortmund as research associate for commercially oriented research in 3D simulation. In 2006, he joined the foundation of Institute for Man-Machine Interaction (MMI) at RWTH Aachen University, Germany as principal investigator and received his doctorate summa cum laude (Dr.-Ing.) from RWTH Aachen University in 2012. For his thesis, he was awarded the "Borchers medal". In 2017, he joined SDU Robotics as Associate Professor at the Mærsk Mc-Kinney Møller Institute (MMMI) at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU). In 2018, he was appointed to take the position of a Full Professor at SDU Robotics.

SPEAKERS

Dr. Dimitrios BILIOURIS

European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)

JOB TITLE

Project Adviser

AFFILIATION

European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)

BIO

Dr Biliouris is an experienced Project Advisor with a demonstrated history of working in the government administration industry. He is a strong administrative professional skilled in Environmental Awareness, Geography, Earth Observation, Raw Materials and European Union Research and Innovation projects and funding.

Jonas BENTZEN

Christiansen & Essenbæk A/S

JOB TITLE

Project Manager

AFFILIATION

Christiansen & Essenbaek (CEAS); Member of Danrep. A danish industry network for clients, engineers, contractors, and suppliers within concrete repairs.

BIO

Jonas has 16 years of experience working in all sorts of concrete constructions as site engineer and later project manager.

Mads ESSENBAEK

Christiansen & Essenbæk A/S

JOB TITLE

Project Manager

AFFILIATION

Christiansen & Essenbaek (CEAS)

BIO

Mads has 23 years of experience working as a manager in concrete construction and with concrete repairs.

Mr. José Carlos Jiménez FERNÁNDEZ

Tecnalia

JOB TITLE

Technologist Researcher

AFFILIATION

Tecnalia

BIO

Msc in Civil Engineering and Finite Element Analysis. Technologist researcher in Tecnalia Research & Development, with active participation in other EU-funded project focused in civil construction research and structural health monitoring.

Fernando Sigchos JIMÉNEZ

European Builders Confederation

JOB TITLE

Secretary General

AFFILIATION

European Builders Confederation (EBC)

BIO

Fernando Sigchos Jiménez is the Secretary General of the European Builders Confederation (EBC), the organisation representing construction crafts and SMEs at the European level. Fernando sits in the Board of Small Business Standards, the EU organisation representing SMEs in standardisation and in the Steering group of the Construction 2050 Alliance. Defending and promoting the interests of micro and small companies in construction, Fernando also sits in the employers' delegation of the European Sectoral Social Dialogue Committee for construction, in the Board of the public-private Built4People partnership on people-centric innovation for a sustainable built environment and attends ECCREDI meetings. Additionally, he is an Alternate member in the Employers' group of the European Economic and Social Committee EESC and participates to the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform. Fernando also supervises EBC's involvement in the EU co-funded projects Beeyonders, HumanTech and BIO4EEB (Horizon Europe), BIM4Ren and BIM-SPEED (Horizon 2020), CondoReno (LIFE) and Construction Blueprint for Skills (Erasmus+). Fernando speaks French, Spanish and English.

Dr. Antidio Viguria JIMÉNEZ

FADA CATEC

JOB TITLE CTO Avionics and Systems

AFFILIATION CATEC (Advanced Center for Aerospace Technologies)

BIO Dr Antidio Viguria (FADA-CATEC), PhD from University of Seville and Head of the Avionics and Systems Dept. of CATEC technological center from 2008 to 2018, and since 2019 CTO in Avionics and Systems at CATEC. He has been researcher from 2006 to 2008 at the Georgia Institute of Technology (Atlanta, USA) granted by Fulbright, working on robotics systems. He is co-author of more than 90 peer reviewed publications. He has more than 15 years of experience in project coordination, having participated as WP leader of FADA-CATEC in more than 25 FP7 and H2020 projects. He has also been project coordinator of more than 60 National R&D Spanish projects related to UAS. He is also currently the Project Coordinator of PILOTING H2020, a project that involves 14 partners and has a budget of around 9M€ for four years. Finally, he coordinates a team of 52 people developing technologies applied to UAS.

Dr. Bharath SANKARAN

Naska.AI

JOB TITLE Chief Technology Officer and Co-Founder, HumanTech WP3 Leader

AFFILIATION Naska.AI (formerly Scaled Robotics)

BIO Dr. Bharath Sankaran is the CTO and co-founder of Naska.AI (formerly Scaled Robotics). Dr. Sankaran is a trained roboticist with expertise in computer vision, machine learning, and manipulation. At Naska.AI, he leads the product and engineering teams that have developed pioneering solutions for construction quality control in complex, highly unstructured construction environments. His research interests lie in applying statistical learning techniques to perception and control problems in 3D vision, active perception, and interactive perception. Dr. Sankaran has degrees in computer science, robotics, aerospace engineering, and mechanical engineering. He received his Ph.D. from the University of Southern California. During his Ph.D., he was a visiting scholar at the Max Planck Institute for Intelligent Systems. He has also worked at the GRASP Lab at the University of Pennsylvania, the Robotics Institute at Carnegie Mellon, and the Space Systems Lab at the University of Maryland. Dr. Sankaran has also worked at various industry research labs which include, Qualcomm Research (San Diego), Mitsubishi Electric Research Labs (Boston), and Bosch Research and Technology Center (Palo Alto).

Patrick ROTH

Implenia

JOB TITLE New Business & Innovation Manager

AFFILIATION Implenia Schweiz AG

BIO Patrick Roth works as a New Business & Innovation Manager at Implenia as part of the Strategic Business Management team in the Division Civil Engineering. Patrick has a background in Business Economics & IT and has a Master's Degree (M.Sc.) from the University of Kaiserslautern Landau (former Technical University Kaiserslautern). Before his time at Implenia, he worked as a Senior IT Consultant and Business Analyst at NTT Data in Stuttgart where he specialized in Model-based Systems Engineering (MBSE) for the Automotive Industry. Patrick also has 5 years of start-up experience as a founder in the Med-Tech sector. Besides his job at Implenia, he holds a position as a co-lecturer at the University of Applied Sciences in Stuttgart.

Dr. Gabor SZIEBIG

SINTEF, HumanTech WP5 leader

JOB TITLE Research Manager

AFFILIATION SINTEF Manufacturing

BIO Gabor Sziebig (Senior Member, IEEE) received the M.Sc. degree in computer science from the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Budapest, Hungary, in 2007, and the Ph.D. degree in production engineering from the Norwegian University of Science (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway, in 2013. He is currently a Research Manager with SINTEF Manufacturing and also part-time Associate Professor with the Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering Science and Technology, UiT The Arctic University of Norway. His research fields are automation, robotics, computer vision, and control theory. During his Ph.D. studies, he was focusing on novel programming methods for Flexible Manufacturing Systems and have developed a concept called small-scale intelligent manufacturing systems (SIMS). He is the Chair of the IEEE IES-Technical Committee on Control, Robotics and Mechatronics, and the Secretary of the IFAC TC on Robotics.